

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Abdulhat Djalilov Turapovich

SYNTHESIS OF A NEW SUPERPLASTICIZER FROM LOCAL RAW MATERIALS

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/IYUN

